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GreenHive

The official **newsletter** of the Green Hive Project

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About the Project

The main objective of the **Green Hive** project is to introduce a new way of thinking and educating about sustainability with an approach founded on systemic innovation. This **Erasmus+ Cooperation Partnership** in Vocational Education and Training (VET), is implemented by partners from Ireland, Italy, Greece, Spain and Romania. A key result will be a **European platform-based Ecosystem for Sustainability Education**.

THE GREEN HIVE ECOSYSTEM

Green Hive is creating a European network to innovate sustainability education. This will be achieved through uniting institutes, students, and communities through active collaboration.

External Stakeholders

The Green Hive external stakeholders comprise of users, the academic world, and the social and private sector who participate in activities of the Green Combs.

Green Combs

The Green Combs are local hubs in vocational training entities. They provide information, insights, and inspiration on sustainability challenges. The Combs connect people and build a local community around sustainability through events, offer learning opportunities to students and external stakeholders and provide opportunities to design innovative solutions through open challenges and workshops.

Green Hive Consortium

The Green Hive consortium includes project partners from Ireland, Italy, Greece, Spain and Romania who coordinate the ecosystem and provide capacity development opportunities, hackathons, and contests for the hubs.

PROJECT RESULTS

Four main results will be co-developed with over 500 VET experts in the scope of the project.

- 1 Methodological Framework
- 2 Toolkit for Green Combs
- 3 Educational Resources
- 4 The Green Hive Platform

RESULTS OF THE METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

Phase 1 of the Green Hive project has concluded! This phase consisted of research and development of the Methodological Framework for creating a European sustainability education ecosystem.

The [Comparative Report on Sustainable Education in Vocational Education and Training \(VET\) in Europe](#) outlines the key findings and conclusions of the research, undertaken in the 5 partner countries, regarding the current strengths and weaknesses in Sustainable Education in VET and assessing the current status and best practices in the development of the knowledge, skills and attitudes defined by GreenComp.

WHAT CAN BE FOUND IN THE COMPERATIVE REPORT?

Common themes emerged throughout the research.

Educators from all regions emphasised their **interest in developing sustainability competencies in vocational education and training (VET)**, calling for individual leadership within educational institutions and integration into curricula.

The rise of digital learning and climate awareness greatly fuels the growing interest in sustainable practices.

Challenges include educators' dedication in an already busy environment, inadequacies in current practices, and institutional barriers.

Furthermore, limited resources, resistance to change, and the need for robust monitoring tools are also identified as obstacles.

Benefits of sustainable competencies include contributions to sustainable economies and shaping a greener future. Staff training, dedicated resources, and practical methodologies are crucial, while collaboration with external partners is highlighted for success.

Aligning education with Sustainable Development Goals is deemed essential for societal well-being and addressing global challenges.

The result of the comparative report offers an introductory document to inform the development of a "**Methodological Framework**", a "**Toolkit for the setup and management of Green Combs**", "**Educational resources for Green Combs**", and the "**Green Hive**" platform based on the results of the extensive research.

You can read the full Comparative Report, as well as the National Reports from Ireland, Italy, Greece, Spain and Romania on the project website greenhiveproject.eu

Check out the Methodological Framework on the next page.

METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

A EUROPEAN PLATFORM-BASED ECOSYSTEM FOR SUSTAINABILITY EDUCATION

COMPONENTS & FUNCTIONS OF THE ECOSYSTEM

MANAGING PARTY

Who: The Green Hive **Project Consortium**

Role:

- Coordinates the ecosystem
- Provides **capacity-building opportunities, hackathons** and **contests** for the Hubs
- Provide **knowledge-transfer spaces** and **co-creation activities**

GREEN COMBS

Who: **VET institutions**, as **local sustainability education hubs of the Green Hive**

Role:

- Provide **information, insights and inspiration** on sustainability within and outside their institutions
- Connect people and build a local community around sustainability through **events**
- Provide **learning opportunities** to students and external stakeholders
- Provide opportunities to design innovative solutions via **open challenges** and **workshops**

EXTERNAL PARTIES

Who: **External stakeholders**, such as representatives of civil society organisations, companies, Adult, School and Higher Education institutions

Role:

- **Participate in the Combs' activities thus contributing to the sustainability education actions of the hubs**

INTERACTION BETWEEN THE PARTIES & WORK FACILITATION

DIGITAL PLATFORM

The platform will include:

- A **Resources** section, collecting the educational resources developed in the project, a User Manual for the Combs' coordinators, open to submissions from the hubs;
- An **Activity co-creation tool** to let the hubs co-design with their students, local stakeholders and/or other hubs, learning activities for sustainability education;
- A **Contest management tool** to let the hubs launch and manage hackathons and competitions on sustainability challenges;
- An **Event section**, collecting virtual events promoted by the consortium and the hubs about sustainability education;
- **Profile pages** of the 15 local hubs we have to establish during the project (e.g., information about the hubs, opportunities to collaborate on projects and initiatives);
- An **Interactive map** showing the hubs' location.

BEST PRACTICES

Researchers gathered **50 best practices** from the partner countries. Below are a few examples. You can explore all 50 resources on [the project website](#).

The **Take 1 Programme**, funded by the department of Education in Ireland, is promoted as a mechanism for embedding Education for Sustainable Development in learning and teaching in second level schools. It aims to support schools to communicate, raise awareness of, and embed Education for Sustainable Development as part of a broad curriculum, through the UN Sustainable Development Goals.

GECO For School is a free green education programme hosted in a virtual environment that allows direct interaction through avatars with which each student can glimpse and explore first-hand content related to the world of sustainability and concerning the topics of renewable energy, eco-food, green mobility, circular economy and sustainable tourism.

Green Week is a national programme by the Romanian Ministry of Education. It is in line with the provisions of the report on Climate Change and Environmental Education in Sustainable Schools, prepared by the working group of the Presidential Administration, the National Strategy on Education for Sustainable environment and climate change 2023-2030.

The **New Sustainability Module for VET in Spain** developed by Naturgy Foundation, aims at enhancing professionals' job readiness through updated energy sector training. The initiative integrates Sustainability modules into Spain's VET curricula by 2024-2025 and its success factors include strategic alignment, stakeholder engagement, and resource provision.

WHAT'S NEXT

We are currently working on the next phase of **Green Hive**. This includes preparation for the **ONLINE CO-CREATION LAB** to be held by the partners on **January 30th** and involves Working Groups from each of the partner countries.

Would you like to learn more? Reach out to us anytime via the project website greenhiveproject.eu if you have any questions or would like more information.